

CHARACTERIZATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF MICROPLASTICS IN COMPOST SAMPLES IN SELECTED COMPOST SITES IN THE WESTERN PROVINCE, SRI LANKA

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Microplastics (MPs), small plastic particles measuring less than 5 millimeters, have garnered significant attention in aquatic ecosystems, yet their presence and impact in soil environments remain relatively understudied. Compost can significantly improve soil quality by enhancing its structure, increasing nutrient content, and promoting beneficial microbial activity. However, compost may pose a risk of soil contamination with microplastics if derived from solid waste dumping sites. Therefore, the present study aimed to determine the contamination of microplastics in composts derived from five composting sites (Karadiyana dumping site, Kotikawatta pradeshhiya sabha, Seetawakapura urban council, Kaduwela municipal council, and Seetawaka pradeshhiya sabha) in the western province of Sri Lanka. Compost samples were digested with Fenton reagent and density separated using a saturated sodium chloride solution in the laboratory. Subsequently, samples were filtered through 0.45µm membrane filters and observed for microplastics using a stereo microscope (x40 magnification). Enumerations of microplastics were performed for color and types. To confirm the chemical compositions of the extracted particles, FT-IR spectroscopy was done. Results revealed that the contamination of the average amount of microplastics in the compost samples was high (4150±300.2 items/kg), and all the samples were contaminated with MPs. The highest contamination was observed in the Karadiyana sample (2750±195.6 particles/kg), and the lowest contamination was recorded from Kaduwela municipal council (330±28.8 particles/kg). According to the types of MPs, filaments, and fragments were highly recorded (3450±851.9 items/kg and 700±42.4 items/kg, respectively), and blue color was the most dominant MP color found among these particles (2820±834.4 items/kg). Polypropylene (PP) was the dominant polymer of detected MPs from different samples. Polystyrene (PS), Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), and Polyethylene (PE) were the most common polymer types found in sites. Thus, the municipal solid waste compost was a significant source of microplastics, which can contaminate agricultural soil. Therefore, it's important to take the necessary actions to reduce MP contamination at compost sites.

Keywords: *Microplastics, Compost, Western Province, Abundance, Colors and types*